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ALCOHOL REHABILITATION: RIGHT TREATMENT AND NEW BEGINNING

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ABSTRACT

To assess the effectiveness and outcomes of alcohol rehabilitation, in this study was carried out by considering and analysing the collect demographic data of patients such as age, sex, occupation, education, and obtain information on history of addiction, assess the type of treatment given to the patient and conclude the effectiveness of treatment. It is a prospective study will be conducted for a period of 6 months in the department of medicine at Neel Jeer hospital, Thadithota, Rajamahendravaram, we are includes the two hundred Patients and finally data will be collecting from the patient case reports and Standard Questionnaire from and analysed by using statistical significance by student spss-20. We are Includes all people who are undergoing treatment at alcohol rehabilitation centre and those who willing to participate in the study. We are concluding that the alcohol rehabilitation with enrolled patients was found to be effective. The income or profit which is procured by the government by selling of liquor is a direct loss to third part of the population, this comes under first category.

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INTRODUCTION

Is alcohol a tonic or a toxin? The question is especially critical to older people, whose overall medical picture gives alcohol the potential to be a health benefit or a life-shortening hazard. a colorless volatile flammable liquid which is the intoxicating constituent of wine, beer, spirits, and other drinks, and is also used as an industrial solvent and as fuel, any organic compound whose molecule contains one or more hydroxyl groups attached to a carbon atom.⁽⁶⁾ Alcohol comes from fermenting starches and sugars. Alcohol has about 7 calories per gram. These are considered "empty" calories because alcohol contains no beneficial nutrients, such as vitamins and minerals. "Hard" liquors contain about 40% alcohol and tend to be higher in calories.⁽⁷⁾ The present research work aims at the alcohol rehabilitation with enrolled patients was found to be effective. The income or profit which is procured by the government by selling of liquor is a direct loss to third part of the population, this comes under first category. Many head of the families are addicted to Alcohol over a region in Rajahmundry for a period of 6 months.

Alcohol Abuse

Alcohol abuse is a former psychiatric diagnosis in which there is frequent harmful use of ethanol despite its negative consequences. In 2013 it was reclassified as alcohol use disorder (alcoholism) along with alcohol dependence.

Alcohol Addiction

Alcohol Addiction is a state characterized by obsessive engagement in satisfying stimuli, despite adverse consequences. It can be thought of as a disease or biological process leading to such behaviours.

Alcohol Dependence

Alcohol dependence is a previous psychiatric diagnosis in which an individual is physically or psychologically dependent upon drinking alcohol. In 2013 it was reclassified as alcohol use disorder (alcoholism) along with alcohol abuse in DSM-5.

Alcoholism Statistics

When juvenile teens decide to drink, it expenses the health care system approximately \$3.7 billion per year to treat those injured in motor vehicle accidents and suicide attempts. When teens choose to drink alcohol, the total cost to society is about \$52.8 billion.

Alcoholism and Genetics

Chronic use of alcohol leads to fluctuations in brain chemistry especially in the GABAergic system. Various variations occur such as changes in gene expression and down regulation of GABA receptors. During acute alcohol withdrawal, changes also occur such as up regulation of alpha4 containing GABA receptors and down regulation of alpha1 and alpha3 containing GABA receptors.

Alcoholism Disease

Alcoholism is a chemical/biological disease that is primary, progressive, chronic and fatal. The modern disease theory of alcoholism states that problem drinking is sometimes caused by a disease of the brain, characterized by altered brain structure and function.⁽⁸⁾

History

Historically the name "dipsomania" was coined by German physician Dr.C. W. Hufeland in 1819 before it was superseded by "alcoholism". That term now has a more specific meaning. The term "alcoholism" was first used in 1849 by the Swedish physician Magnus Huss to describe the systematic adverse effects of alcohol. Mid 16th century: french (earlier form of alcohol), or from Medieval Latin, from arabical-kuhl 'the kohl'. In early use the term referred to powders, specifically kohl, and especially those obtained by sublimation; later 'a distilled or rectified spirit' (mid 17th century).

India's Biggest Drinkers:

The nssso's 2011-12(national sample survey) consumption data splits per capita weekly consumption of alcohol into four categories – toddy, country liquor, beer and foreign/ refined liquor or wine⁽⁹⁾

- Today is the most popular drink for rural India followed by country liquor.
- The biggest toddy and country liquor-drinking states are Dadra & Nagarhaveli, Arunachal Pradesh and Andaman & Nicobar Islands.
- Andhra Pradesh tops the bigger states, followed by Assam, Jharkhand and Bihar.
- The biggest beer, wine and refined/ foreign liquor drinking states and UTS are Daman & Diu, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Dadra & Nagarhaveli, Arunachal Pradesh, Sikkim and Puduchery.
- Andhra Pradesh and then Kerala and Karnataka tied in third place.
- Andhra Pradesh is by far India's biggest drinking state, consuming 665 ml per capital per week on average, or nearly 34.5 liters per year.
- Kerala is far behind, at 196 ml per week or just 10.2 liters per year.

Effects of Alcohol

1.9.1 on Brain:

- Interferes with coordination and clear thinking.
- Triggers off psychiatric problems ranging from depression to hallucinations, delusions.
- Permanent damage to brain cells.

1.9.2 on Stomach:

- Interferes with digestion.
- Irritates the lining causing gastritis and ulcer
- Increases the incidence of cancer.

1.9.3 on Liver:

- It takes an hour to breakdown one drink of alcohol.
- Excessive drinking is a strain on the liver and can cause
- Fatty liver
- Inflammation of the cells.
- Hepatitis
- Cirrhosis.

1.9.4 on Heart:

- Rhythm and functioning are affected.
- Heart muscles become weak reducing the pumping efficiency.

1.9.5 on Skin:

- Premature ageing, wrinkles and rosacea are common side effects.
- Dehydrating and dilates capillaries under the skin, causing them to break.

1.9.6 on Hair:

- Dehydrating effects of alcohol can leave hair dry, brittle and prone to breakage

1.9.7 on Eyes:

- Blood vessels in the eyes are likely to break, which causes blood-shot looking eyes.

1.9.8 on Weight:

- Drinking just five pints of beer a week is the equivalent of eating 221 doughnuts a year. Alcohol is extremely fattening because it is essentially sugar. It can cause rapid weight gain, which is linked to other health problems such as diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease.

1.9.9 Other Problems:

- Neuritis
- Damage to the nerve endings causing tingling, numbness or tremors.
- Pancreatitis.
- Inflammation and damage of pancreas.⁽¹⁰⁾

Pathophysiology

Alcohol's rewarding and reinforcing (i.e., addictive) properties are mediated through its effects on dopamine neurons in the meso limbic reward pathway, which connects the ventral segmental area to the NAcc. One of alcohol's primary effects is the allosteric inhibition of NMDA receptors and facilitation of GABAA receptors (e.g., enhanced GABAA receptor-mediated chloride flux through allosteric regulation of the receptor). At high doses, ethanol inhibits most ligand gated ion channels and voltage gated ion channels in neurons as well.

With acute alcohol consumption, dopamine is released in the synapses of the mesolimbic pathway, in turn heightening activation of postsynaptic D1 receptors. The activation of these receptors triggers postsynaptic internal signaling events through protein kinase. A ultimately phosphorylate CREB, inducing CREB-mediated changes in gene expression With chronic alcohol intake, consumption of ethanol similarly induces CREB phosphorylation through the D1 receptor pathway, but it also alters NMDA receptor function through phosphorylation mechanisms; an adaptive down regulation of the D1 receptor pathway and CREB function occurs as well. Chronic consumption is also associated with an effect on CREB phosphorylation and function via postsynaptic NMDA receptor signalling cascades through a MAPK/ERK pathway and CAMK-mediated pathway. These modifications to CREB function in the meso limbic pathway induce expression (i.e., increase gene expression) of Δ FosB in the NAcc, where Δ FosB is the "master control protein" that, when over expressed in the NAcc, is necessary and sufficient for the development and maintenance of an addictive state (i.e., it's over expression in the nucleus accumbens produces and then directly modulates compulsive alcohol consumption).

(11)(12)(13)(14)

Mortality

Alcohol consumption increases the risk of various cancers, hypertension, liver disease, unintentional injuries, and violence. (15)(16). Definitions of light and moderate alcohol consumption varies, but these levels of consumption are generally found to decrease the risk of ischemic heart disease. (17)

For all cause mortality the relation is typically U shaped, with non-drinkers and heavier drinkers having higher risks than light and moderate drinkers. (18). The royal colleges of physicians, psychiatrists, and general practitioners have therefore advised men and women to drink less than 21 and 14 units a week, respectively, whereas the UK government has recommended no more than 4 and 3 units a day, respectively; 1 unit is 8-10 g of alcohol. (19)(20). However, the levels giving the lowest or a low risk are likely to vary with age as well as sex and have not been systematically quantified. (21). Methods to compute risks of all cause mortality we required data on cause specific relative risks, distribution of alcohol consumption, and distribution of causes of death. Substantially increased risks of all cause mortality can occur even in people drinking lower than recommended limits, and especially among younger people. (22)

Alcohol-Related Deaths

- Nearly 88,000 people (approximately 62,000 men and 26,000 women) die from alcohol-related causes annually, making it the third leading preventable cause of death in the United States.
- In 2013, alcohol-impaired driving fatalities accounted for 10,076 deaths (30.8 percent of overall driving fatalities). (1)

Alcoholism in India

Alcohol is banned in some parts of India such as Manipur and Gujarat, but it is legally consumed in the majority of states. There are believed to be 62.5 million people in India who at least occasionally drink alcohol. Unlike many western countries the consumption of alcohol in India is witnessing a dramatic rise – for instance, between 1970 and 1995 there was a 106.7% increase in the per capita (this means per individual in the population) consumption. International brewers and distillers of alcoholic beverages are keen to become popular in India, because it is potentially offers the third largest market for their product globally. India has also become one of the largest producers of alcohol – it produces 65% of alcoholic beverages in South-East Asia. Drinking Statistics for India Indians prefer hard liquors and distilled spirits over beers – 80% of consumption involves these stronger beverages. It is suggested that 20% of the population has at least tried alcohol. In the past two decades the number of people who have consumed alcohol has moved from 1 in 300 to 1 in 20. The Lancet reported that more than half of those who consume alcohol in India would fall into the category of hazardous drinking.

It has been suggested that there are a worryingly 14 million people in India who would be described as dependent on alcohol and in need of help. Another concern is the increasing tendency to engage in binge drinking where people deliberately become intoxicated. (23)

Alcohol kills one Indian every 96 minutes. (25) 3 Deaths per day were alcohol related. (24)

Alcohol Rehabilitation Definition

Alcohol rehabilitation is the process of combining medical and psychotherapeutic treatments to address dependency on alcohol. Specifically, alcohol rehab is a treatment process/protocol used when a person who has used alcohol excessively or abused alcohol discontinues their use with the goal of remaining permanently abstinent. The treatment process usually includes detoxification, rehab, and maintenance of sobriety. (1)

Advantages

Structure

There is some truth to the saying “idle hands are the devils workshop.” An inpatient program aims to give little free time for a recovering addict to contemplate how to get or use drugs. The less time someone’s mind has to think about alcohol, the less likely they will relapse.

Removal of Negative Influences

An inpatient facility generally limits phone calls and only allows visitors for a few hours on the weekend. This policy keeps a patient insulated from people who may trigger or encourage their addiction.

Constant Support

Individuals undergoing recovery live at an inpatient rehab program and therefore reap the benefits of 24-hour medical and psychological support from an experienced staff.

No Access

Unlike an outpatient program, where an individual returns home in the evening and is susceptible to the craving to use, there are no alcohol or drugs on the premises of an inpatient facility. Therefore, easy access to relapse is removed.

Medical Supervision

Withdrawal from certain addictions can have potential lethal consequences without the appropriate medical support.

Depending on the type of substance being abused and the length of the addiction, the body may need medical monitoring and pharmaceutical assistance to ease symptoms.

Protection for Loved Ones

Since there is limited contact with family and loved ones during inpatient rehab, they are spared witnessing the emotional and physical roller coaster that can be a part of the beginning phases of becoming sober.

Focus On Self

In an inpatient facility, an individual has the ability to concentrate completely on their own recovery without any distractions or stresses of typical daily life.

Camaraderie

Friendships are allowed to develop between patients as they live and work together towards the healthy common goal of sobriety. This helps to keep the feelings of loneliness and isolation at bay that can destroy someone's attempt at recovery.

Variety of Therapeutic Options

Inpatient rehab provides numerous opportunities to explore alternative therapeutic options such as yoga, meditation, acupuncture, exercise programs and massage that may become a healthy outlet for daily stresses once intensive addiction treatment has finished.

Nutritional Assistance

Eating well can help clear the mind and support the body through the initial detox phases and throughout the recovery process. ⁽²⁾

Confidentiality

Some alcohol abusers often have the unfounded fear that alcohol treatment centres may reveal information about their problems to third parties. That is so untrue. These centres know the implication of that and will not disclose any information about you or the problems you are having to any third party unless, perhaps, when a court demands for such.

Provision of Aftercare

Some alcohol treatment centres also provide aftercare, or what some other people usually refer to as prolonged care. When talking about addiction, one can almost not speak with certainty that an addict will not fall back into his or her alcohol abuse issue. It is in order to take care of this possible relapse that aftercare is often needed.

This will make it possible for a patient to continue receiving assistance, when needed, from a treatment facility after they might have been discharged from such a facility. As part of aftercare, alcohol treatment centres also monitor patients to see how well they are putting into use every coping skill they have been imparted while undergoing their treatment.

These are not all the advantages of alcohol treatment centres; there are more. But with the few ones mentioned, you probably can tell they provide Effective Avenue toward successful alcohol rehabilitation. ⁽³⁾

Disadvantages

Of course, there is no one particular recovery option that has all benefits with no down sides. There are two major drawbacks to opting for a self-pay option:

The costs –

These facilities are upwards of thousands of dollars for recovery treatment. This makes them inaccessible for patients who do not have those finances available or are unable to borrow it or secure a loan. Even though there is no denying that recovery is an investment, it is one that the patient has to be able to repay in his or her lifetime. Otherwise, they may find themselves free of dependence, but burdened with debt. The additional stress brought on by debt may serve as a trigger to bring on a relapse.

The locations –

Even though traditional facilities are available throughout the nation, you may have to search a bit harder for a good self-pay recovery program. This may make it difficult to find a facility nearby or one that is within a reasonable distance for potential family visits. ⁽⁴⁾

Goals

Discard All of Your Drug or Alcohol-Related Items

Maybe you had a few flasks or bottles hidden in your home, your car, or even the desk draw of your office. Perhaps you had needles, spoons, ties and lighters – even empty pill bottles littered in coat pockets, purses, or cabinets. These entire serve as reminders of your past – preventing you from looking forward and focusing on your goals.

No matter how strong you may feel at this moment, these items can be triggers in weaker moments, and will remind you of what your brain may be craving.

Delete Your Dealer's Contact Info

Even though you may be fresh out of drug addiction rehab, people you once smoked or used with are still out there – and they're still using. They're in your stored contact numbers and your text messages, just waiting for you to answer. Delete, block and distance yourself – even if it means getting a new phone and a new number.

Find a Recovery Sponsor and/or a Local Support Group

Finding allies in your recovery is crucial to laying a solid foundation for the long term. For some people, a local network is the best solution – for others, staying engaged with a sponsor or fellow graduate may mean contact through text, phone calls or social media. Set your goal to find the right solution for you.

Restore Positive Relationships

Often, people in recovery from drug or alcohol addiction find that they burned bridges with friends or family members while actively addicted. Rebuilding relationships won't be an immediate goal; it will take time and commitment. However, manage your goals by restoring each relationship one person at a time, one step at a time. Rebuilding a relationship after rehab starts with communication – whether it is in person, by phone, text, email, or even in a handwritten note. Just like the small stones were used to move the mountain, set small goals within each relationship you wish to rebuild.

Commit to One Positive Action Each Day

What qualifies as a positive activity may differ from person to person, however – some examples may include journaling, exercising, cooking a new meal, meditating, praying – or a combination of various actions and activities. The point is to commit to one thing per day that will cue positivity in your life.

Try New Things

Too much idle time isn't good for anyone. Being willing and open to trying new things will help you find a new hobby – or reignite passion for an old one. Make a list of things you'd like to try or things that you miss doing, and set aside time to do them. ⁽⁵⁾

Alcohol Rehab Program

Alcohol rehab programs may be residential (a person lives on site during treatment) or outpatient. They all have these elements in common:

Initial assessment:

When a person is first admitted to an alcohol rehab program, he or she receives a thorough clinical assessment. The assessment is then used to help determine the best approach to treatment. It is also used to help develop the treatment plan.

During the initial assessment, a counsellor will ask questions about:

- The amount of alcohol a person drinks
- How long the person has been using alcohol
- Cultural issues around the use of alcohol
- The effect alcohol has had on the person's life
- Medical history
- Current medical problems or needs
- Medications being taken
- Mental health or behavioral issues
- Family and social issues and needs
- Legal and financial issues the person is confronting
- Educational background and needs
- Current living situation
- Home environment
- Employment history, stability, problems, and needs
- Previous experience with rehab or attempts to quit using alcohol

If it's determined during the initial assessment that there are urgent medical issues that need to be addressed or that the person needs a detox program, the person will be referred to a doctor who will oversee this part of the person's care.

Development of a Plan

Following the assessment and, if needed, a detox program or other medical care, the person will be assigned a counsellor or case manager. Together, they will work out a detailed treatment plan that identifies problems, goals, and details about how to address the problems and reach the goals. That plan will be carried out by a team of trained individuals that can include a social worker, counsellor, nurse, psychologist, psychiatrist, or other professional.

Motivation

Plays an important role in alcoholism treatment by influencing patients to seek, complete, and comply with treatment as well as make successful long-term changes in their drinking. Both alcohol-abusing and alcohol-dependent people can be classified into different “stages of change” in terms of their readiness to alter their drinking behaviour. Consequently, researchers have had to consider more seriously the role of motivation in the treatment of and recovery from substance abuse and to incorporate motivational enhancement strategies into treatment programs.⁽²⁶⁾

Group and Individual Counselling

Counselling is an integral part of the treatment for alcoholism. Counselling gives the individual in rehab tools to accomplish important goals:

- Overcome denial
- Recognize problems
- Become motivated to solve problems
- Address mental health issues such as depression or anxiety disorders
- Change behavior and create a recovery life.
- Re-establish healthy connections with family and friends
- Build new friendships with people who don't use alcohol

Individual Assignments

Throughout the rehabilitation process, the person will be given materials to read, listen to, and watch, will be asked to write about his or her experiences or responses to treatment, and given new behaviours to try.

Education about Substance Use Disorders

Often, people who have a substance use disorder like alcoholism are in a state of denial, believing their drinking is normal. In order to progress in recovery, they need to confront the fact that they do have a problem with alcohol and acknowledge the dangers that the problem present.

Life skills training

When someone who has been dependent on alcohol goes into recovery, he or she may need training in these areas: managing anger, stress, or frustration; employment skills; goal setting; spending leisure time; developing social and communication skills; and managing money and time.

Relapse Prevention Training

It's important that the person recovering from alcoholism learn to recognize situations that can trigger a relapse and how to avoid them.

Orientation to Self-Help Groups

Most alcohol rehab programs require participants to join a self-help group after the program ends to help them continue on the path of recovery. Taking part in a self-help group is not considered part of treatment, but rather an essential part of maintenance.⁽²⁷⁾

Management Of Alcoholism

Three medications have been FDA-approved for treating alcohol addiction and a fourth, topiramate, has shown promise in clinical trials (large-scale studies with people). The three approved medications are as follows:

Naltrexone blocks opioid receptors that are involved in the rewarding effects of drinking and in the craving for alcohol. It reduces relapse to heavy drinking and is highly effective in some patients. Genetic differences may affect how well the drug works in certain patients.

Acamprosate (campral) may reduce symptoms of long-lasting withdrawal, such as insomnia, anxiety, restlessness, and dysphoria (generally feeling unwell or unhappy). It may be more effective in patients with severe addiction.

Disulfiram (antabuse) interferes with the breakdown of alcohol. Acetaldehyde builds up in the body, leading to unpleasant reactions that include flushing (warmth and redness in the face), nausea, and irregular heartbeat if the patient drinks alcohol. Compliance (taking the drug as prescribed) can be a problem, but it may help patients who are highly motivated to quit drinking.⁽²⁸⁾⁽²⁹⁾

Fighting Alcoholism with Medication

Antabuse

Antabuse was approved for the treatment of alcoholism more than 50 years ago, making it the oldest such drug on the market. It works by interfering with the body's ability to absorb alcohol -- specifically by inhibiting production of an enzyme that would otherwise allow the body to absorb an alcohol breakdown product called acetaldehyde after even a small amount of alcohol is ingested, resulting in extremely unpleasant side effects that can include flushing, nausea, and palpitations.

Naltrexone

Naltrexone helps to both reduce the pleasure that alcoholics receive from drinking and the cravings that compel them to seek out more alcohol. It does so by blocking receptors (docking sites) in the brain for endorphins, proteins produced by the body that help to elevate mood. The same receptors also accept narcotics such as morphine and heroin. The drug can be taken as a once-daily pill or in a recently approved once-monthly injectable form. In clinical trials, oral naltrexone was shown to reduce the amount of relapses to heavy drinking (defined as four or more drinks per day for women, five or more for men). Compared with patients who took a placebo (dummy pill), alcoholics who took naltrexone had 36% fewer heavy drinking episodes over a three-month period. In the COMBINE (Combining Medications and Behavioural Interventions for Alcoholism) study, sponsored by the National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (NIAAA), naltrexone was found to be as effective as up to 20 sessions of alcohol counselling by a behavioural specialist, when either was administered under a doctor's close supervision. Naltrexone is now available in a once-monthly injectable form called Vivitrol. The advantage of this formulation is that patients are more likely to stick with a drug they only need to take once a month, and it appears to work very well.

Campral

Campral, taken by mouth three times daily, acts on chemical messenger systems in the brain. It appears to reduce the symptoms that alcoholics may experience when they abstain from booze over long periods. These symptoms can include insomnia, anxiety, restlessness, and unpleasant changes in mood that could lead to relapse. In European clinical trials and in pooled data from several studies, Campral increased the proportion of alcoholics who were able to refrain from drinking for several weeks or months.

Topamax

Topamax is approved by the FDA for the treatment of seizures but not for alcoholism. It has a mechanism of action similar to that of Campral and may similarly help patients avoid or reduce the symptoms associated with long-term abstinence. In a study published in *The Journal of the American Medical Association* in October 2007, researchers from the U.S. and Germany reported that Topamax was better than placebo at reducing the percentage of heavy drinking days over a 14-week period.

Treating Alcoholism

Drugs Alone Aren't Enough "All these medications work best in the context of psychosocial treatment. Just giving somebody pills without that is not as effective," says Herman. According to Weiss, at least three forms of psychosocial therapy have been shown to be effective at treating alcoholism, with roughly similar success rates. These include:

- Cognitive behavioral therapy, a form of psychotherapy focusing on identifying and modifying negative thoughts and thought patterns.
- Motivational enhancement therapy, a patient-centered approach in which counselors try to get patients to think about and express their motivations for change and to develop a personal plan that can help them make the necessary changes.⁽³⁰⁾

Alcohol Withdrawal

Alcohol withdrawal symptoms can begin as early as two hours after the last drink, persist for weeks, and range from mild anxiety and shakiness to severe complications, such as seizures and delirium tremens (also called DTs). The death rate from DTs which are characterized by confusion, rapid heartbeat, and fever is estimated to range from 1% to 5%.

Because alcohol withdrawal symptoms can rapidly worsen, it's important to seek medical attention even if symptoms are seemingly mild. Appropriate alcohol withdrawal treatments can reduce the risk of developing withdrawal seizures or DTs.

It's especially important to see a doctor if you've experienced previous alcohol withdrawal episodes or if you have other health conditions such as infections, heart disease, lung disease, or a history of seizures.

Causes of Alcohol Withdrawal Syndrome

Heavy, prolonged drinking -- especially excessive daily drinking -- disrupts the brain's neurotransmitters, the brain chemicals that transmit messages.

For example, alcohol initially enhances the effect of GABA, the neurotransmitter which produces feelings of relaxation and calm. But chronic alcohol consumption eventually suppresses GABA activity so that more and more alcohol is required to produce the desired effects, a phenomenon known as tolerance.

Chronic alcohol consumption also suppresses the activity of glutamate, the neurotransmitter which produces feelings of excitability. To maintain equilibrium, the glutamate system responds by functioning at a far higher level than it does in moderate drinkers and non-drinkers.

When heavy drinkers suddenly stop or significantly reduce their alcohol consumption, the neurotransmitters previously suppressed by alcohol are no longer suppressed. They rebound, resulting in a phenomenon known as brain hyper excitability. So, the effects associated with alcohol withdrawal -- anxiety, irritability, agitation, tremors, seizures, and DTs -- are the opposite of those associated with alcohol consumption.

In general, how severe alcohol withdrawal symptoms become depends on how much and for how long a person has been drinking.

Minor alcohol withdrawal symptoms often appear 6 to 12 hours after a person stops drinking. Sometimes a person will still have a measurable blood alcohol level when symptoms start.

These symptoms include:

- Shaky hands
- Sweating
- Mild anxiety
- Nausea
- Vomiting
- Headache
- Insomnia

Between 12 and 24 hours after they stop drinking, some patients may experience visual, auditory, or tactile hallucinations.

These usually end within 48 hours. Although this condition is called alcoholic hallucinosis, it's not the same as the hallucinations associated with DTs. Most patients are aware that the unusual sensations aren't real.

Withdrawal seizures usually first strike between 24 and 48 hours after someone stops drinking, although they can appear as early as 2 hours after drinking stops. The risk of seizures is especially high in patients who previously have undergone multiple detoxifications.

DTs usually begin between 48 and 72 hours after drinking has stopped, Risk factors for DTs include a history of withdrawal seizures or DTs, acute medical illness, abnormal liver function, and older age.

Symptoms of DTs, which usually peak at 5 days, include:

- Disorientation, confusion, and severe anxiety
- Hallucinations (primarily visual) which cannot be distinguished from reality
- Profuse sweating
- Seizures
- High blood pressure
- Racing and irregular heartbeat
- Severe tremors

Treatment of Alcohol Withdrawal Syndrome

If you have mild to moderate withdrawal symptoms, your doctor may prefer to treat you in an outpatient setting, especially if you have supportive family and friends. Outpatient detoxification is safe, effective, and less costly than inpatient detoxification at a hospital or other facility. However, you may require inpatient treatment if you don't have a reliable social network, are pregnant, or have a history of any of the following:

- Severe withdrawal symptoms
- Withdrawal seizures or DTs
- Multiple previous detoxifications
- Certain medical or psychiatric illnesses

The goals of treatment are threefold: reducing immediate withdrawal symptoms, preventing complications, and beginning long-term therapy to promote alcohol abstinence.

Prescription drugs of choice include benzodiazepines, such as diazepam (Valium), chlordiazepoxide (Librium), lorazepam (Ativan), and oxazepam (Serax). Such medications can help control the shakiness, anxiety, and confusion associated with alcohol withdrawal and reduce the risk of withdrawal seizures and DTs. In patients with mild to moderate symptoms, the anticonvulsant drug carbamazepine (Tigerton) may be an effective alternative to benzodiazepines, because it is not sedating and has low potential for abuse.

To help manage withdrawal complications, your doctor may consider adding other drugs to a benzodiazepine regimen. These may include:

- An antipsychotic drug, which can help relieve agitation and hallucinations
- A beta-blocker, which may help curb a fast heart rate and elevated blood pressure related to withdrawal and reduce the strain of alcohol withdrawal in people with coronary artery disease
- Clonidine (Catapres), another blood pressure drug
- Phenytoin (Dilantin), an anticonvulsant which doesn't treat withdrawal seizures but may be useful in people with an underlying seizure disorder

Preventing Future Alcohol Withdrawal Episodes

Because successful treatment of alcohol withdrawal syndrome doesn't address the underlying disease of addiction, it should be followed by treatment for alcohol abuse or alcohol dependence. He or she also may recommend joining a 12-step group -- such as Alcoholics Anonymous and Narcotics Anonymous -- or staying at a comprehensive treatment facility that offers a combination of a 12-step model, cognitive-behavioural therapy, and family therapy.⁽³¹⁾

Aims and Objectives

In The study we assess The Effectiveness and Outcomes of Alcohol Rehabilitation. The Study Was Carried Out By Considering The Following Objectives. To Analyze The Effectiveness And Outcomes Of Alcohol Rehabilitation.

- To collect demographic data of patients such as age, sex, occupation, education etc.
- To obtain information on history of addiction.
- To assess the type of treatment given to patient.
- To conclude the effectiveness of treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Materials**

- Case sheets of patients
- Questionnaire

Source of Data

Data will be collected from the patient through the questionnaire from the NEEL JEER hospital, Thadithota, Rajamahendravaram.

Method of Collection of Data**Study Site:**

Study will be conducted at department of medicine at NEEL JEER hospital, Thadithota, Rajamahendravaram.

Study Duration

The study will be conducted for a period of 6 months.

Study of Design

It is a prospective study.

Study Criteria

The study will be carried out by considering following criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Includes all people who are undergoing treatment at alcohol rehabilitation centre.
- Patients willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Alcoholics who are not undergoing treatment.
- Alcoholics in general public.
- Non alcoholics.

Analysis of Data

A prospective study will be analysed for statistical significance by student spss-20

Study Procedure

A prospective study will be carried out at medicine department of NEEL JEER hospital, Thadithota, Rajamahendravaram, after getting ethical clearance from institutional ethics committee and with the prior permission from department of medicine. The patient admitted to the department of medicine will be enrolled into the study considering the study criteria after taking their consent to participate into the study. From the enrolled patients the data will be collected from the case sheets, questionnaire and other relevant resources in a suitably designed data collection form.

RESULTS**Age Group Analysis**

A total of 200 alcoholics were enrolled into the study out of which 37(18%) patients were in the age range between 15-25 years,104(52%) patients were in the age range between 25-35 years,50(25%) patients were in the age range between 35-45years,5(2%) patients were in the age range between 45-55 years,3(2%) patients were in the age range between 55-65years and 1(1%)in the age range between 65-75years.

Table No.1.

AGE RANGE	NUMBER OF PATIENTS (n=200)	PERCENTAGE (%)
15-25	37	18
25-35	104	52
35-45	50	25
45-55	5	2
55-65	3	2
65-75	1	1

Figure No.1 based on the analysis of age distribution.

Occupational Status

Among 200 patients, 25 (13%) patients were students, 43 (22%) patients were daily wage workers, 13(7%) patients were labor, 10(5%) patients were cement workers, 14(7%) patients were electricians, 24 (12%) patients were farmers, 22(11%) patients were drivers, 5(3%) patients were business men, 16(8%) patients were mechanics, 4 (2%) patients were gate keepers, 2(1%) assistant contractors, 9(5%) patients were shopkeepers, 2(1%) patients were unemployed, 5 (3%) patients were salesmen, 3(2%) patients were teachers, 3(2%) patients were paper mill agents.

Table No.2 Occupational Status of the patients.

Category	Number Of Patients N =200	Percentage
Married	150	75
Unmarried	50	25

Figure No.2 Based On the Analysis of Occupational Status Of Patients.

Marital Status

Among 200 patients, 150(75%) patients were married and 50(25%) patients were unmarried.

Table No.3 Shows Marital Status of the patients.

Years Of Consuming	Number Of Patients N= 200	Percentage (%)
1-10	163	81
10-20	31	16
20-30	6	3

Figure No.3 Based On The Analysis Of marital Status Of The Patients.

YEARS OF CONSUMING

Among 200 patients, 163(81%) patients were consuming from 1-10 years, 31(16%) patients were consuming from 10-20 years and 6(3%) patients were consuming from 20-30 years.

Table No.4 Shows Years of Consuming Of Patients.

OCCUPATION OF THE PATIENT	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Students	25	13
Daily wage workers	43	22
Labor	13	7
Cement workers	10	5
Electrician	14	7
Farmer	24	12
Driver	22	11
Business man	5	3
Mechanic	16	8
Gate keeper	4	2
Assistant contractor	2	1
Shopkeeper	9	5
Unemployed	2	1
Sales man	5	3
Teacher	3	2
Paper mill agent	3	2

Figure No.4 Based On the Analysis of Years of Consuming.

Amount of Alcohol Consuming Every Day

Out of 200 alcoholics, 168(84%) patients were consuming quarter, 27(13%) patients were consuming half, 3(2%) patients were consuming full and 2(1%) patients were consuming unlimited.

Table No.5 Shows Amount of Alcohol Consuming Every Day.

Quantity Of Alcohol	Number Of Patients N= 200	Percentage (%)
≤180 ml	168	84
≤375 ml	27	13
≤750 ml	3	2
Unlimited	2	1

Figure No.5 Base on the Analysis of Amount of Alcohol Consuming Every Day.

Number of Times/Day

Among 200 patients, 43(21%) patients were taking once a day, 70(35%) patients were taking twice a day, 54(27%) patients were taking thrice a day and 33(17%) patients were taking quarterly.

Table No.6 Shows Number of Times/Day in Patients.

NUMBER OF TIMES /DAY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n= 200	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	43	21
2	70	35
3	54	27
4	33	17

Figure No.6 Based On the Analysis of Amount of Alcohol Consuming Every Day.

Quality of Alcohol

Out of 200 alcoholics, 87(43%) patients were consuming branded, 68(34%) patients were consuming cheap and 45(23%) patients were consuming both branded and cheap.

Table No.7 shows Quality of Alcohol in patients.

QUALITY OF ALCOHOL	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Branded	87	43
Cheap	68	34
Both	45	23

Figure No.7 Based On the Analysis of Quality of Alcohol.

Health Complications

Among 200 alcoholics, 23 (11%) patients were with health complications and other 177 (89%) patients were without health complications.

Table No.8 Shows Health Complications of the Patients.

HEALTH COMPLICATIONS	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	23	11
No	177	89

Figure No.8 Based On the Analysis of Health Complications.

Past Medical History

Among 200 alcoholics, 200(100%) patients were without any past medical history.

Table No.9 Shows past Medical History of the Patients.

Past Medical History	Number Of Patients N =200	Percentage (%)
Yes	0	0
No	200	100

Figure No.9 Based On the Analysis of Past Medical History.

Past Medication History

Out of 200 alcoholics, 199(99%) patients were without past medication history and 1(1%) patient was with past medication history.

Table No.10 Shows past Medication History of The Patients.

PAST MEDICATION HISTORY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	1	-1
No	199	100

Figure No.10 Based On the Analysis of Past Medication History.

Home Life

Among 200 alcoholics, 140(70%) patients were unhappy with their home life.

Table No.11 Shows Home Life of the Patients.

HOME LIFE	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Happy	60	30
Unhappy	140	70

Figure No.11 Based On the Analysis of Home Life.

Shy with People

Out of 200 alcoholics, 30(15%) patients were with shy and 170(85%) patients were without shy.

Table No.12 Shows Shy With People of the Patients.

SHY WITH PEOPLE	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	30	15
No	170	85

Figure No.12 Based On the Analysis of Shy with People.

Affecting Reputation

Among 200 alcoholics, 116(58%) patients were with reputation effected and others 84(42%) patients were without reputation effected.

Table No.13 Shows Affecting Reputation of the Patients.

AFFECTING REPUTATION	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	116	58
No	84	42

Figure No.13 Based On the Analysis of Affecting Reputation.

Financial Difficulties

Out of 200 alcoholics, 108(54%) patients were with financial difficulties and 92(46%) patients were without financial difficulties.

Table No.14 Shows Financial Difficulties Of The Patients.

FINANCIAL DIFFICULTIES	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	108	54
No	92	46

Figure No.14 Based On the Analysis of Financial Difficulties.

Crave At a Definite Time

Among 200 alcoholics, 99(50%) patients crave at a definite time and 101(50%) patients doesn't crave at a definite time.

Table No.15 shows Crave at a Definite Time of the patients.

CRAVE AT A DEFINITE TIME	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	Percentage (%)
Yes	156	78
No	44	22

Figure No.15 Based On the Analysis of Crave At a Definite Time.

Need to Drink At Next Morning

Out of 200 alcoholics, 105(52%) patients need to drink at next morning and 95(48%) patients doesn't need to drink at next morning.

Table No.16 Shows Need To Drink At Next Morning in the Patients.

NEED TO DRINK AT NEXT MORNING	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	105	67
No	95	33

Figure No.16 Based On the Analysis of Need to Drink at Next Morning.

Difficulties in Sleeping

Among 200 alcoholics, 32(16%) patients were having difficulties in sleep and 168(84%) patients were not having difficulties in their sleep.

Table No.17 shows Difficulties in Sleeping in the patients.

DIFFICULTIES IN SLEEP	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	32	16
No	168	84

Figure No.17 Based on the analysis of difficulties in sleeping.

Escape from Worries

Out of 200 alcoholics, 28(14%) drink to escape from worries and 172(86%) drink casually.

Table No.18 Shows Escape from Worries of the Patients.

ESCAPE FROM WORRIES	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	28	14
No	172	86

Figure No.18 Based on the analysis of escape from worries.

Drink Alone or With Company

Among 200 alcoholics, 45(22%) patients drink alone, 147(74%) patients drink with company and 8(4%) patients drink both alone and with company.

Table No.19 Shows Drink Alone or With Company of the Patients.

DRINK ALONE /COMPANY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Alone	45	22
Company	147	74
Both	8	4

Figure No.19 Based On the Analysis of Drink Alone or With Company.

Complete Loss of Memory

Out of 200 alcoholics, 39(19%) patients were with complete loss of memory and 161(81%) patients were without loss of memory.

Table No.20 shows Complete Loss of Memory of the patients.

COMPLETE LOSS OF MEMORY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	39	19
No	161	81

Figure No.20 Based On the Analysis of Complete Loss of Memory.

Feeling Sweaty

Among 200 alcoholics, 75(37%) patients were feeling sweaty and 125(63%) patients were not feeling sweaty.

Table No.21 Shows Feeling Sweaty Of the Patients.

FEELING SWEATY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	75	37
No	125	63

Figure No.21 Based On the Analysis of Feeling Sweaty.

Shaking Hands

Out of 200 alcoholics, 75(37%) patients having shaking hands and 125(63%) patients were without this symptom.

Table No.22 Shows Shaking Hands of the Patients.

SHAKING HANDS	NUMBER OF PATIENTS n=200	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	75	37
No	125	63

Figure No.22 Based On the Analysis of Shaking Hands.

Physician Ever Treated

Among 200 alcoholics, 5(2%) patients were already treated by other physicians and 195(98%) patients were for the first time.

Table No.23 Shows Physician Ever Treated In The Patients.

PHYSICIANS EVER TREATED	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
n=200		
Yes	5	2
No	195	98

Figure No.23 Based On the Analysis of Physician Ever Treated.

Condition of the Patient

Out of 200 alcoholics, 8(4%) patients were out patients and 192(96%) patients were in patients.

Table No.24 Shows Condition of the Patient.

IP/OP	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
n=200		
OP	8	4
IP	192	96

Figure No.24 Based On the Analysis of Condition of the Patient.

Statistical Evaluation

Table No: 25 Shows Statistical Evaluation of the Patient Data.

S.NO.	PARAMETER	MEAN±STANDARD DEVIATION	P value
1.	Psychology01 - Psychology02	422.73 ± 86.13	P = 0.0002
2.	Social01 - Social02	170.20±160.60	P = 0.4958
3.	Personal01 - Personal02	433.57±133.49	P < 0.0001

Out of 200 patients, the process of rehabilitation resulted in the decrease of AWARE score with which the therapy was maintained for 48 weeks study the changes in psychological parameters (mean±SD) from base line (422.73±86.13) (Pvalue=0.0002); Social parameters (mean±SD) from base line (170.20±160.60) (Pvalue=0.4958) and personal parameters(mean±SD) from base line(433.57±133.49)(Pvalue<0.0001) where statistical analysis showed the mean and standard deviation(mean±standard deviation) , were found to be statistically significant. The Pvalue for psychological and personal parameters were shown significant and social parameters for the patients were not so significant which can result in relapse of alcoholism.

Based On The Analysis Of Before And After Treatment In Psychological, Social And Personal Aspects In Sub Division Of The Aware Questionnaire.

Figure No: 25 Shows Based On The Analysis Of Before And After Treatment In Psychological, Social And Personal Aspects In Sub Division Of The Aware Questionnaire data collected from the patients.

Cronbach's alpha is arguably the most commonly used metric to evaluate the internal consistency reliability associated with scores derived from a scale. In cases where important decisions are being made based on scores from a scale, a reliability in excess of .90 should be expected. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for internal consistency reliability for any scales or subscales one may be using. Cronbach's alpha does not provide reliability estimates for single items. In our study, 28 clustered as a robust single factor with excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha: 0.94).

Table No: 26 Based On the Analysis Of Before and After Treatment in Psychological, Social and Personal Aspects in Sub Division of the Aware Questionnaire Data Collected From the Patients.

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.94	.305	28

DISCUSSION

Cronbach's alpha is arguably the most commonly used metric to evaluate the internal consistency reliability associated with scores derived from a scale. In our study, 28 clustered as a robust single factor with excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha: 0.94). Comparing our results with the study conducted by WR Miller & RJ Harris in USA especially in New Mexico, we found that pattern of 28 clustered as a robust single factor with excellent internal consistency. (Cronbach's alpha: 0.92-0.93). We didn't find any difference in our study when compared with these two studies. In our study Age group of 25-35 years (104) are more prone to Alcoholism. Age group of 65-75 years (1) are less prone to Alcoholism. In our study Daily wage workers (43) are more alcoholic and Assistant contractors (2) and unemployed (2) are less alcoholic. Among 200 patients, 150(75%) patients were married and 50(25%) patients were unmarried where married are more alcoholic. In our study patients consuming alcohol for a span of 1-10 years (163) are more and 20-30 years (6) are less. According to our study the patients consuming quarter (168) are high and unlimited (2) are least. In our study patients consuming 2 times per day are more (70) and 4 times per day are least (33). According to our study patients consuming branded alcohol are high (87) and patients consuming both branded and cheap are low (45). In our study patients without health complications are more (177) and patients with health complications are less (23). Among 200 alcoholics, 200(100%) patients were without any past medical history. Out of 200 alcoholics, 199(99%) patients were without past medication history and 1(1%) patient was with past medication history. Among 200 alcoholics, 200(100%) patients were unhappy with their home life. Out of 200 alcoholics, 30(15%) patients were with shy and 170(85%) patients were without shy. In our study patients effected reputation are more (116). In our study patients with financial difficulties are consuming more alcohol (108) and without financial difficulties are less (92). In our study more number of patients (156) craves at a definite time and less number of patients (44) do not crave at a definite time. In our study patients need to drink at next morning are more (163) and patients doesn't need to drink at next morning are less (37). Among the study group 168 patients are not having difficulties in their sleep and 32 patients are having difficulties in their sleep. In our study 172 patients drink casually and 28 patients drink to escape from worries. Among the study group 147 patients drink with company and 8 patients drink both alone and company. Among the study group 161 patients are without loss of memory and 39 patients are with loss of memory. In our study 125 patients are not feeling sweaty and 75 patients were feeling sweaty. In our study patients (75) experiencing shaking hands are more and (125) patients are not experiencing shaking hands. Among the study group patients treated for the first time are (195) more and patients already treated by other physicians are (5) less. Among the study group 192 patients were treated as inpatients and 8 patients were treated as outpatients.

Classification of Aware Questionnaire

Around 28 questions of aware questionnaire in the due course of study which were further classified into 3 subgroups based on symptoms, which were further categorised into psychological, social and personal. Based on Psychological aspects, before Rehabilitation 25th question gives the highest score (1265) and 4th question gives the least score (1100); after Rehabilitation 17th question gives the highest score (884) and 3rd question gives the least score. Based on Social aspects, before rehabilitation 26th question gives the Highest score (1215) and 18th question gives the Least score (893); after Rehabilitation 1st question gives the Highest score (992) and 26th question gives the Least score (890).

Based on Personal aspects, before Rehabilitation 24th question gives the Highest score (1292) and 16th question gives the Least score (1170); after Rehabilitation 28th question gives the Highest score (975) and 8th question gives the Least score (568). Out of 200 patients, the process of rehabilitation resulted in the decrease of AWARE score with which the therapy was maintained for 48 weeks study the changes in psychological parameters (mean \pm SD) from base line (422.73 \pm 86.13) (pvalue=0.0002); social parameters (mean \pm SD) from base line (170.20000 \pm 160.60) (pvalue 0.49) and personal parameters (mean \pm SD) from base line (433.57 \pm 133.49) (pvalue<0.0001) where statistical analysis showed the mean and standard deviation, were found to be statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

We are conclude that the alcohol rehabilitation with enrolled patients was found to be effective. The income or profit which is procured by the government by selling of liquor is a direct loss to third part of the population, this comes under first category. Many head of the families are addicted to it. The money they need to spend for medical expenses, the problems they face by the death of the head of the family, the debt they make for that person, all these will come under second category. The p value for psychological and

personal parameters were shown significant and social parameters for the patients were not so significant which can result in relapse of alcoholism. Hence, it is the prime responsibility of the people to avoid taking of liquor voluntarily. People should be educated about the effects of alcoholism which can help the individual to voluntarily reduce the consumption of alcohol this is possible only through Alcohol rehabilitation.

Finally the authors conclude that those who are addicted alcohol they are spend for medical expenses and this problem may lead to death. Further research work can be enhanced by comparing the Alcohol prevalence over a group of population in various zones of state.

Conflict Of Interest

The authors do not have any conflicts of interest.

List of Abbreviations

DSM	-	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual Of Mental Disorders
GABA	-	Gamma-Amino butyric Acid
NACC	-	Nucleus Accumbens
NMDA	-	N-Methyl-D-Aspartate Receptor
CREB	-	Camp Response Element Binding Protein
MAPK	-	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases
ERK	-	Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinases

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